

The Study of Applying Models: House, Temple and School for Sufficiency Development to Participate in ASEAN Economic Community: A Case Study of Trimitra Temple (China Town) Bangkok, Thailand

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Abstract—The purposes of this study are 1) to study the impact of the 3-community-core model: House (H), Temple (T), and School (S) with the co-operation of official departments on community development to ASEAN economic community involvement and 2) to study the procedures and extension of the model. The research which is a qualitative research is based on the formal and informal interviews. Local people in a community are observed. Group interview is, also, operated by executors and cooperators in the school in the community. In terms of social and cultural dimension, the 3-community-core model consisting of house, temple and school is the base of Thai cultures bringing about understanding, happiness and unity to the community. The result of this research is that the official departments in accompanied with this model developers cooperatively work together in the community to support such factors as budget, plan, activities. Moreover, the need of community, and the continual result to sustain the community are satisfied by the model implementation. In terms of the procedures of the model implementation, executors and co-operators can work, coordinate, think, and launch their public relation altogether. Concerning the model development, this enables the community to achieve its goal to prepare the community's readiness for ASEAN Economic Community involvement.

Keywords—ASEAN Economic Community, Community Development.

I. INTRODUCTION

DUETO Thailand's policy to participate in ASEAN community in the year 2015, all sectors and organizations in Thailand have been geared to accomplish the policy of the government. In terms of education, not only English is introduced as a medium of instruction in almost every institution but all learners or students are also required to study cultures and traditions of neighboring countries in prospect of working cooperatively among communities, houses, temples, and school. Naturally schools in old town in Bangkok are located in temple areas and communities to patronize one another and this is the root of Thai social development before the adoption of western style of budget planning and organization development based on administrative law.

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Fig. 1 Trimitra temple, Yaowaraja Bangkok Thailand

Fig. 2 The president of Rom Chatra foundation

Yaowaraja or China Town is a part of old town located in the heart of business area of Bangkok more than 150 years old, and it is very famous for gold smith market, Chinese cuisines, and many others. Not only do tourists always visit the area, but they can also definitely learn ways of living, cross cultures, and various traditions of the Thais, the Chinese, the Indian, and some other nationalities. One of the most outstanding temples in that area is Trimitra Temple where you can pay respect to the 6000 kilograms golden image of Buddha. More than 10,000 tourists call at this temple each day to learn the culture and Thainess. Moreover, this temple provides a primary and secondary school with its popularity in Chinese teaching. Romchat foundation, a patronage of this temple, launched a Chinese classroom named "Kong Je Ker Tang" with the purposes of supporting local activities, and Chinese unity. This enables Trimitra Temple be the center of

local people in the community to work cooperatively with the foundation and the monks. Also “House-Temple-School model” is launched with the aims of carrying out a sufficiency development project to prepare local community to participate in ASEAN economy. Details of the project are as follows:

- 1) The aim of this project is to motivate the cooperation among houses, temple, and school to share both knowledge and experiences to uplift educational management.
- 2) This project allows the management of fiscal budget from various organizations to support the local activities.

Teaching Burmese language in 80 hours to entrepreneurs, leaders, students, and government officers on Sundays by way of communicating between employers and Burmese employees in this area

Launching exhibitions conducted by local child leaders to present cultures, societies, and economy of the 10 ASEAN countries to the public

Organizing the competition concerning ASEAN knowledge among primary and secondary school students

- 3) This project allows the collection of profit from China town to be used in boundaries of the 4 regions of Thailand.

The outcome of this community development project to participate in ASEAN community is interesting in terms of education.

II. OBJECTIVE

The purposes of this study are 1) to study the impact of the 3-community-core model: House (H), Temple (T), and school (S) with the cooperation from official departments on community development to ASEAN economic community involvement, and 2) to study the procedures and the extension of the model.

III. METHODS

A. To Survey the Geographical Area of China Town Based On the Co-Operation of the 3-Community-Core Model:

House (H), Temple (T), and school (S) to synthesize and develop the community model ready for ASEAN Economic Community involvement.

B. To Apply Qualitative Research for Those Who Participate in Group Discussion and Non-Participation

The Director of Romchatra Foundation, headmasters of the schools, students, and 10 representatives from leading schools including interviews with leaders of community, entrepreneurs in Yaowaraj area and tourists.

C. To Synthesize AIC Model to Develop Community Based On Professor Dr. PrawetVasi;

A (Appreciation), The Stage of Appreciation is to determine the frame of administration towards this model by requiring those relevant to present and share their experience and vision.

I (Influence), The Stage of Influence requires those responsible for the 3-community-cores: House (H) refers to the local's collaboration, Temple (T) refers to monasteries as

center of the community, and School (S) refers to a learning center where activities and knowledge can be shared.

Fig. 3 The primary school of Trimitra temple

C (Control), The Stage of Control requires a condition of working leaders responsible for sharing their experiences and their creative thinking.

Based on the theory of the relation and existence of culture in the community [1], and [2] together with The Right of Thai Community found in The Thai Constitution in the year 1997 and 2007, Thai people have developed their lands and communities. Also the theory of Modern Policy [3] also helps to support. According to The Existence of Cultural Community, the background of people and relationship between people and society with friendliness is emphasized. [1] and [4]. From the model to develop temples and schools by applying AIC with the theory of community and local development, this is related to Thai educational management that is focused on environmental conservation and strength of people in community [7].

The study of this research enables the integration of learning management to live together before the adoption of western style covering budget management to achieve the plan. To launch a project for community developing project, it can revive to work like Thai society in the past and connect to alliance among community, temple, school, and Trimitra temple has long been the center of the administration.

IV. EXPECTED OUTCOMES

A. The Working Pattern

The working pattern, which supports departments in order to exchange their attitudes and to make their working plans, and has intellectuals to give some advises and to bring about confidences in working, consists of the collaboration from the influential persons in the area to support grouping in Yaowaratcommunity (China Town). Monk Dhamma Powanawikrom, the assistant abbot of Trimitra temple and the president of Rom Chatra foundation gave an idea called “BorWorRor” or “House, Temple, School”, which means superb and long lasting. The development of education is based on the performance relating to Thai ways of living.

B. Schools can be Responsible for the Provision of ASEAN Knowledge

Students learn about ASEAN in terms of native languages and cultures of the 10 nations in ASEAN. This project

provides ASEAN lesson plans for schools. The details of the lesson plan are as follows;

- 1) School should have the demonstration room about ASEAN knowledge. In the room, there should be ASEAN documents, pictures and audiovisual aids for students to be familiar with the 10 ASEAN nations.
- 2) School should change landscape by installing landmarks in Burmese, English and Thai words.
- 3) Students should create their own club, "Young ASEAN" in each school. The members can demonstrate the ASEAN exhibition to visitors.
- 4) Schools should be the center of resource of knowledge in each community to be ready for ASEAN Economic Community (AEC).
- 5) Teachers and students should work together to create the consciousness of status of Thailand in AEC.

C. The Community Changes Its New Role in Participation to Schools and Temple

The community changes its new role in participation to schools and temple, which raise the status of community to be more modernized and to train people in the community to practice languages of ASEAN neighbors. In Yaowarat there are the most number of Burmese labors, so local people in Yaowarat should learn Burmese cultures and Burmese language in order to live together trustworthily and to be ASEAN people in the future. Important places in Yaowarat should have signs in Burmese language to show the names of those places.

From 2011 to 2012 the project in Wat Tri Mitra or China Town, the pioneer community is managed successfully and the budget of the project is supported by the Quality Learning Foundation. The foundation expands its project to other four areas in each region. The idea of Bor Wor Ror is the fundamental for the project to proceed. Therefore, in 2013 the project is expanded to proceed.

- 1) In the north of Thailand, the project is carried out at Mae Jan School, Chiang Rai, which is located on the border Thailand and Burma.
- 2) In the northeastern of Thailand, the project is carried out at Pi Boonmangsaaharn School, Ubonrachatanee, where people on the border relate to the Vietnamese.
- 3) In the south of Thailand, the project is carried out at Ban Namh Krajai School, Songklah, which is on the border Thailand and Malaysia.
- 4) In the central of Thailand, the project is carried out at Aekachai School, Samut Sakorn, where the most number of Burmese students study.

Many departments which are parts of the project will have a seminar after they finish their works. The seminar concludes lessens as follows:

- 1) The community restores the relationship between temples and schools, and the private department also supports to hold the school activities. In addition, the community can manage its own society to learn about culture, national economic and ASEAN knowledge. As a result, Thais are

urged to speak English and neighbor languages, which will be beneficial in applying for a job and working.

- 2) The new definition of ASEAN citizens is very interesting because the ways of living of people at present and in the future will be peaceful and long lasting in the same region. In addition, the study Thai history is restored into Thai curriculum, especially the part of wars between Siam and Burma, the administration of Siam towards colonial states such as Laos and Cambodia and the loss of territories of Laos and Cambodia under the colonization of France. The restoration of Thai history brings peace and understanding between Thailand and the neighboring countries.

V. CONCLUSION

This study changes the new concept of learning in class. Generally, the duty of school is to teach ASEAN studies in the field of Social Studies. However, the study in Social Sciences applies the concept Baan (House), Wat (Temple) and Rong Rean (School) or Bor Wor Ror in Thai society. The implementation of this concept emphasizes the participation and collaboration of the three parts of the community in the area. Wat Trimitra or Yaowarat is the busy area where Chinese merchants trade in. The Chinese merchant can live peacefully together in Yaowarat with other races. This finding is in line with the research, "The Study of Chinese Community in Bangkok" [5].

Fig. 4 Yaowarat (China town near the Trimitra temple)

The conclusion of research is that when the society has activities which are beneficial to local area and the religion leader such as Monk Dhamma Powanavikrom, an assistant abbot of Wat Trimitra is respected by Chinese people because he has close relationship with Thais and Chinese people for forty years. In addition, Burmese labors in Yaowarat believe in Buddhism, so they can live with Thai-Chinese people peacefully.

Based on the research entitled "The Study of media to promote tourism and culture: Yoowarat Case Study", working together under Thai administration which is relevant to AIC term causes the people in every part in Thai society think together, work together, coordinate and publicize. [6] As a result, they learn how to respect rights, suitability, and benefits to the project and the area study. In addition, the project supports the education of juvenile and leads to optimistic

attitude in living together in ASEAN. It is relevant to ASEAN motto, "Every nation in ASEAN is One Community."

The implementation of the model Baan, Wat, and RongRuan was successful in WatTrimitra area or China Town and in other four regions of Thailand. This model is a long lasting developing administration and can be adapted by those in the neighbor countries such as Laos, Burma, Cambodia and other countries where people believe in Buddhism. Muslim countries also use this model, but they use mosque to be the center of community.

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